

Cheliceral flashing not only in wolf spiders (Araneae: Lycosidae)

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ABSTRACT: Cheliceral flashing describes the behaviour during which a spider tilts its prosoma to expose red setae on its chelicerae, which are otherwise not visible. It was first reported in the Lycosidae of the genus *Hogna* and in particular for *H. spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898). We report here on cheliceral flashing that was also observed in members of Ctenidae (*Anahita* sp.) and Stasimopidae (*Stasimopus coronotus* Hewitt, 1915).

Key words: cheliceral setae, Ctenidae, Lycosidae, Stasimopidae

INTRODUCTION

Warning coloration (aposematism) is prominent in the animal kingdom, and spiders are no exception. The bright red and orange, often against a black background, in *Latrodectus* species is one example. There is, however, a trade-off between blending in with the environment versus standing out due to displaying bright warning colours. This is especially true for some ground-living spiders.

Ground-living spiders have colours that blend in with the soils or leaf litter of their habitat; bright coloration would advertise themselves to predators and would therefore be selected against. If the spider was, however, able to hide the bright colours and only display when needed, it would allow the spider to be camouflaged when not in danger, but display its aposomatic colours when threatened. The sudden display of colour would also startle a predator. A dense patch of orange-red hairs on the ventral side of the prosoma where the fangs are (Fig. 1) is particularly distinct within the Mygalomorphae. Several mygalomorph families rear up when threatened, which in turn expose this red patch of setae, which is normally hidden on the ventral side, as a warning (Fig. 2). This has been observed in the Theraphosidae (Fig. 1) and some Idiopidae genera (Fig. 2).

Similar to that, but more striking, is the flashing of red setae of the chelicerae. Cheliceral flashing describes the behaviour during which a spider tilts its prosoma to expose red setae on its chelicerae, which are otherwise not visible (Webb, 2013). As the spider tilts its prosoma, the intensity of the red increases from a pinkish colour to a fiery orange-red colour (Fig. 3), thereby changing the apparent colour of the chelicerae from the (usually earthy) colour that are similar to the rest of the prosoma, to a bright orange-red colour.

Cheliceral flashing was first reported in the Lycosidae of the genus *Hogna* and in particular for *H. spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) and *H. transvaalica* (Simon, 1898) (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Webb, 2022). This behaviour was observed in both males and females. In exuviae it could be seen that the red setae cover the top two-thirds of the chelicerae.

NEW RED CHELICERAE OBSERVATIONS

OBSERVATION 1: While sampling spiders for the NSF-funded *Biodiversity of the Waterberg Mountain Complex*, at Welgevonden Game Reserve, in Limpopo, South Africa, a hitherto unknown example of cheliceral flashing was observed, and the spider was collected and photographed (Figs 4–6). The species was identified as an *Anahita* species (Ctenidae) but unfortunately no *Anahita* species have yet been listed from South Africa. The voucher specimen, a male, is deposited in the Ditsong Museum as a voucher specimen. The orange-red setae on the chelicerae cover the top two-thirds of the chelicerae.

Figure 1. *Augacephalus junodi* (Simon, 1904) (Theraphosidae), with a close-up of the chelicerae to indicate the red patch of setae below the fangs. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 2. *Idiops gunningi* (Hewitt, 1913) (Idiopidae) in a defense position, which displays the red patch of setae that are normally hidden on the ventral side. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figure 3. *Hogna spenceri* (Pocock, 1898) (Lycosidae) from Lephale displaying the red setae on the chelicerae. Photo credit: Peter Webb.

Figures 4–6. *Anahita* undetermined sp. Ctenide male: (4–5). Display of cheliceral flashing when threatened. (6) When not threatened. Photo credits: C. Warmenhove & M. Aucamp.

OBSERVATION 2: As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012; 2015), surveys are undertaken throughout the country. The fifth author (PW) was involved in surveys at Lephahlale in Limpopo, South Africa. He photographed all the species collected and while handling the species he observed that some specimens display the red setae on their chelicerae when disturbed. Two of the specimens, a female (Fig. 7) and male (Fig. 8), were identified as an *Anahita* species. The chelicerae bear orange-red setae but less intense as the specimen from Welgevonden. The Lephahlale specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida as voucher specimens.

Figures 7–8. Undetermined *Anahita* sp. (Ctenidae) from Lephahlale. 7. Female displaying the orange-red chelicerae. 8. Male. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

OBSERVATION 3: While P. Webb photographed the material sampled at Lephahlale, he observed similar red setae on the chelicerae of a Stasimopidae specimen. The species was identified as *Stasimopus coronatus* Hewitt, 1914 (Fig. 9). Here the red setae are present on the bottom half of the chelicerae (Figs 10–11).

CONCLUSION

Cheliceral flashing could prove to be more widespread in spiders than initially thought. If present in taxa from such different clades as the Araneomorphae and the Mygalomorphae, then it might be an example of convergent evolution in warning predators. It might be a method used by some burrow dwellers to scare off enemies.

REFERENCES

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Figures 10–11. Colour of chelicerae setae visible on *Stasimopus coronatus* female from Lephahlale, South Africa. Photo credits: Peter Webb.